

EARTH SCIENCES

IDENTIFICATION OF GRADIENT ZONES ACCORDING TO GRAVITY PROSPECTING DATA

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Abstract

As is known, new digital instruments have now been developed for more reliable measurements of the gravimetric field, which also provides a more accurate division of the gravitational field into local maxima and minima. There are various methods for transforming and filtering gravimagnetic anomalies, which differ from each other in the sensitivity of field separation. The most sensitive of them are the gradient methods and the methods of higher derivatives, which make it possible to identify small variations in gravitational and magnetic anomalies and linearly elongated gradient zones. These anomalies may be associated with zones of faults and disturbances, as well as the accumulation of hydrocarbons and the presence of ore deposits. At the Department of Geophysics of ASOIU, algorithms and programs for identifying such anomalies on a computer have been developed. The article analyzes some results on identifying such zones on model profile and area materials.

Keywords: anomaly, gradient zones, field transformation, transformation palette, derivative method, local anomaly, observed field, algorithm.

Introduction

The observed gravimagnetic field is usually complex, as it consists of local and regional field components that correspond to local and regional geological structures. Local structures are geological objects of small size and located at shallow depths in sedimentary strata. Regional objects make up the deep structure of the earth's crust.

There are various methods for transforming and filtering gravimagnetic fields, such as a graphical method for identifying anomalies along a profile, a method of averaging over an area or over a profile, the Sachsov-Nygaard gradient method, and the method of higher derivatives. methods of analytical continuation of fields, etc. [9-10]. The initial data are the results of observations of gravitational and magnetic fields along a profile or area.

The method of gradients and higher derivative ones, as well as corresponding filtering methods, are the most sensitive methods and are capable of identifying gradient zones and areas of change in the potential field. At the Department of Geophysics of ASOIU, algorithms and programs for identifying such anomalies on a computer have been developed [2]. Gradient and higher arbitrary methods are very popular nowadays and are used to solve a wide range of geological problems [1,4-8].

Methods for processing the initial gravitational field

The Sachsov-Nygaard area gradient method uses a palette with two radii - internal and external (Fig. 1). The gravity field gradient is calculated using the formula [10]:

Fig.1. Transformation palette with two radii

$$\Delta g_{\text{grad}} = \frac{\Delta \bar{g}(R_1) - \Delta \bar{g}(R_2)}{R_2 - R_1} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta \bar{g}(R) = \frac{\sum_i^n \Delta g_i}{n} \quad (2)$$

Here R_1 and R_2 are the internal and external averaging radii; $\Delta \bar{g}(R_1)$ and $\Delta \bar{g}(R_2)$ are the average values of the gravity field at the corresponding averaging radii.

The radius of the circles depends on the task at hand. The larger the radius, the greater the depth of exploration. The average values of the gravity field at the corresponding averaging radii are calculated as follows:

Here n is the number of points on the palette; Δg_i - the value of gravity at points around the palette.

Currently, this transformation method is carried out on a computer. In this case, to enter field values into a computer, the original field is first quantized by interpolation at the nodes of a square grid (Fig. 2), and then digitally entered into the computer.

Fig.2. Field quantization nodes

Among the methods of higher derivatives, the method of third derivatives of gravity, the Elkins method, has become widespread. This method uses multiple radii. The third derivative of gravity potential is calculated using the following formula [9]:

$$W_{zzz} = \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial z^2} = \frac{1}{64R^2} [44g(0) + 16\bar{g}(R) - 12\bar{g}(R\sqrt{2}) - 48\bar{g}(R\sqrt{5})], \quad (3)$$

where $g(0)$ is the value of the gravity anomaly in the center of a circle of radius R ; $\bar{g}(R)$, $\bar{g}(R\sqrt{2})$, $\bar{g}(R\sqrt{5})$ are averaged values of gravity anomalies along the circles R , $R\sqrt{2}$, $R\sqrt{5}$.

As you can see, a circular palette with three circles with different radii is used here.

The Department of Geophysics developed the Forse–Fortran programs SAXOV and WZZZ, which were used to process the gravitational field model [4-

8]. The processing also used various filtering of the gravitational field model using gradient methods of various directions using the SURFER program.

Results of processing gravitational field models.

To work with the SAXOV, WZZZ and SURFER programs, a model of the gravitational field of the Byandovan area of the Lower Kura depression was used (Fig. 1)

Fig.1. Model of the gravitational field of the Byandovan area

As can be seen here, an areal gravimetric survey was carried out along 15 profiles and, based on them, an initial gravity map with a cross section of 0.5 mGal was constructed [3]. The field is characterized by negative isoanomaly values. In the northern part of the area, a large gravity minimum with an amplitude of 9 mGal, oriented in the north and northwest direction, is clearly visible. Gravity values decrease from -1 mGal to -10 mGal in a northerly direction. In general, the field is complicated by numerous local anomalies and gradients.

For subsequent conversion, the original map was digitized in the "Digit" mode of the SURFER graphic program, and then a grid was created, on the basis of which maps of the original gravitational field model were built in 2D and 3D versions in a modern interface (Fig. 2-3).

To identify gradient zones and sections, at the beginning, the gravitational field of the Byandovan area was filtered in 2D and 3D versions using the SURFER program in the "Gradient directional filter, South (3x3)" mode, on the basis of which the corresponding map was built in 2D and 3D versions (Fig. 4-5). As you can see, the map clearly shows positive gradient areas with different intensities $(1.3-0.8) \times 10^{-6}$ мГал/см mGal/cm, oriented in the northeast and east directions, as well as an intense minimum of negative values of gravity gradients $(0.4 -0.6) \times 10^{-6}$ mGal/cm in the northern part of the area is oval in shape and somewhat

elongated in the eastern direction. The same picture (Fig. 6-7) is observed on the constructed map of the first derivative of the gravitational field of the area in 2D and 3D versions (Order 1 derivative filter, Roberts Row director (3x3)).

Next, the gravity field of the study area was quantized in a uniform square grid of (1x1) cm in size on a map scale to prepare the initial data for the developed programs at the Department of Geophysics. Below are the results of processing using the WSZ program for calculating the total horizontal gravity gradient (Fig. 8-10). As can be seen on the map of total gradients, there are two maxima of the total gradient in the northeastern part of the study area, oriented in the eastern and northern directions with a maximum intensity of the order of 1.45×10^{-6} mGal/cm.

On the map of the second derivatives of gravity obtained using the WZZZ program in the northeastern part, an intense minimum of the second negative derivatives of gravity is clearly visible, and in the rest of the area there are three large maxima with an intensity of $(35-25) \times 10^{-11}$ mGal/cm² of various orientations (Fig.11-13). And finally, the following shows the results of the transformation of the gravity field of the study area using the SAXOV program, which allows you to calculate residual anomalies using the Saxow-Nygaard method (Fig. 14-16). As you can see, this map reflects the same picture as the WZZZ map, but in less detail.

Fig.2. Map of the gravitational field of Byandovan Square in 2D version (in mGal isolines)

Fig.3. Map of the gravitational field of Byandovan Square in 3D version (in mGal isolines)

Fig.4. Map of the gravitational field gradient of the Byandovan area in 2D version in isolines 10^{-6} mGal/cm (Gradient directional filter, South (3x3))

Fig.5. Map of the gravitational field gradient of the Byandovan area in 3D version in isolines 10^{-6} mGal/cm (Gradient directional filter, South (3x3))

Fig.6. Map of the first derivative of the gravitational field of the Byandovan area in 2D version in isolines 10^{-6} mGal/cm (Order 1 derivative filter, Roberts Row director (3x3))

Fig.7. Map of the first derivative of the gravitational field of the Byandovan area in 3D version in isolines 10^{-6} mGal/cm (Order 1 derivative filter, Roberts Row director (3x3))

0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	1.2	0.8	0.6	1	0.7
0.5	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.5	1.4	1.2	0.6	1.2
0.6	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.8	0.8	1.4
0.6	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.9	1.4
0.6	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8
0.5	0.5	0.6	0.8	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.5	0.4
0.5	0.9	1	1	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.6	0.5
0.6	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.8	1	0.7
0.6	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.8	0.8
0.7	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.8

Fig.8. Values of the total gradients of the gravitational field of the Byandovan area in units of measurement 10^{-5} mGal/cm (Force-Fortran programm WSZ)

Fig.9. Map of full gradients of the gravitational field of the Byandovan area in 2D version in isolines 10^{-6} mGal/cm (Force-Fortran programm WSZ)

Fig.10. Map of gravitational field gradients of the Byandovan area in 3D version in isolines 10^{-6} mGal/cm (Force-Fortran programm Saxsow)

-1.1	-1.6	6.6	-0.3	-32.4	-105.3	-97.6	-60	28.4
-3.7	0.2	13.5	35.2	22.7	4	-68.2	-112.1	-16.9
1.6	-2.7	-5.5	-18.2	4.7	8.9	-35.2	-103.9	-39.5
13.5	7.4	-1.9	-19	-12.3	-16.1	-46.5	-68.4	11.6
23.4	21.6	-1.9	-15.8	-13.5	-19	-33.4	-49	13.5
13.4	-16.9	-25.2	-26.3	-8.9	-1.3	-15	-37.3	-24.4
0	-8.7	-6.3	12.3	16.8	3.9	-9.2	-54.5	-56
8.7	15.5	25.2	24	13.4	6.9	-4.8	-29.8	-48.5
4.4	20.2	17.4	8.2	0	-5.6	-5	-15.5	-33.1
6.1	18.1	12.7	1.5	-10.8	-21.8	-16.3	-22.6	-43.9

Fig. 11. Values of gradients of the gravitational field of the Byandovan area in units of measurement 10^{-11} mGal/cm² (Force-Fortran programm WZZZ)

Fig. 12. Map of the second derivatives of the gravitational field of the Byandovan area in 2D version in isolines 10^{-11} mGal/cm² (Force-Fortran programm WZZZ)

Fig. 13. Map of the second derivative of the gravitational field of the Byandovan area in 3D version in isolines 10^{-11} mGal/cm² (Force-Fortran programm WZZZ)

0	0	0	0	-2.7	-1.5	-6.3	-7.7
0.3	0.1	1	0.1	-0.1	-3.1	-5.6	-6.2
0.5	0.3	0	1.2	0.5	-1.6	-6	-4.9
1	0.5	-0.5	-1	-0.8	-1	-4.1	-4.9
1.4	0.1	-0.5	-1.1	-1.1	-0.5	-2.7	-3.7
-0.1	0.1	-1	-0.7	-0.5	-0.8	-2.5	-4
0.3	0.3	0.3	-0.1	0.3	0.3	-2.2	-3.3
0.5	1.5	1.1	1.5	1.1	0.3	-1	-2.6
0.7	1.2	1.1	1.2	0.3	-0.1	-1	-2.2

Fig. 14. Values of gradients of the gravitational field of the Byandovan area in units of measurement 10^{-6} mGal/cm (Force-Fortran programm SAXOW)

Fig. 15. Sachsov-Nygaard gradient map of the gravitational field of the Byandovan area in 2D version in isolines 10^{-6} mGal/cm (Force-Fortran programm SAXOW)

Fig. 16. Sachsov-Nygaard gradient map of the gravitational field of the Byandovan area in 3D version in isolines 10^{-6} mGal/cm (Force-Fortran programm SAXOW)

Conclusions:

1. Gradient methods and higher derivative methods make it possible to identify small variations in gravity anomalies and linearly elongated gradient zones that may be associated with mineral accumulations.

2. Algorithms for calculating gravity gradients using the Sachsov-Nygaard and third vertical derivatives methods are analyzed. gravity. The initial data of the study area have been prepared for working with the Force-Fortran programs SAXOV, WZZZ and WSZ using the Saxov-Nygaard method, third vertical derivatives. gravity and full gravity gradient, developed at the Department of Geophysics of ASOIU,

3. Using the example of the gravitational field model of the Byandovan area, the original field was filtered using the gradient method and the first derivative of the gravitational field of the Byandovan area in 2D and 3D versions (Order 1 derivative filter, Roberts Row director (3x3) and Order 1 derivative filter, Roberts Row director (3x3)) using the SURFER program.

4. Based on the filtering results, gradient maps of the gravitational field model of the Byandovan area were constructed and analyzed in 2D and 3D versions. Positive gradient areas with different intensities ($1.3-$

0.8) $\times 10^{-6}$ mGal/cm, oriented in the northeastern and eastern directions, as well as an intense minimum of negative values of gravity gradients ($0.4 -0.6$) $\times 10^{-6}$ mGal/cm) in the northern part of the square is oval in shape and somewhat elongated in the eastern direction.

5. The values of gravity gradients were calculated using the Sachsov-Nygaard method, third vertical derivatives gravity potential and the full gravity gradient using the SAXOV, WZZZ and WSZ programs and the corresponding grids of the resulting transformans were prepared for constructing the corresponding maps using the Surfer gravity program.

6. Maps of third vertical derivatives, total gradient and residual gravity anomalies (gradients) of the gravitational field model of the Byandovan area in 2D and 3D versions were constructed and analyzed. On the maps of total gradients and gradients of residual anomalies (Sachsov-Nygaard), two maximum gradients are noted in the northeastern part of the study area, with an intensity of about 1.45×10^{-6} mGal/cm. On the WZZZ map in the northeastern part, an intense minimum of the second negative derivatives of gravity is clearly visible, and in the rest of the area there are three large maxima

with an intensity of $(35-25) \times 10^{-11}$ mGal/cm² of various orientations.

References

1. Al-Banna A.S., Al-Kaisy S.A. Using of Gradient Techniques for Depth Estimation of Gravity Source Tikrit Journal of Pure Science Vol. 11 No.(1) 2006, p.8.
2. Jafarov Kh.D., Tsimelzon I.O., Amiraslanov T.S. and others. Methodological guidelines for performing laboratory work on gravimagnetic prospecting and electrical prospecting on a computer. Baku, AZ-INEFTEKHIM, 1981, 28 p. (in Russian).
3. Gadyrov V.G. Application of gravi-magnetic exploration in the search of oil-gas structures in the Kura basin of Azerbaijan. Baku: "Law" publishing house - 2010, 224 p.,12 (in Azerbaijani).
4. Isgandarov Elkhan. Transformation of gravimagnetic anomalies. Proceedings of the International PARCECO scientific conference organized by the Azerbaijan-French University (UFAZ), operating under the Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, November 30 - December 1, Baku, 2021, p.13.
5. İsgandarov E.H. Digital processing of gravimagnetic data. Proceedings of Azerbaijan international geophysics conference. Management of Geophysics, Baku, 2017, 1p.
6. Iskandarov E. H., You Yunlong You Ligu. Transformation of gravitational anomalies by methods derivatives and gradients. Danish Scientific Journal, № 21,2019, pp.13-16.
7. İsgandarov E.H. Digital modeling of gravity gradients for solving structural problems and direct hydrocarbons search. XII Azerbaijan International Geophysics Conference "The role of geophysical research in the exploitation of hydrocarbon resources in the caspian region and similar geological provinces" Dedicated to the 100th Anniversary of the birth of National Leader Heydar Aliyev, April 26-28, 2023, p.2.
8. İsgandarov E.H., Isgandarova L.E. Application of computer technology to solve the problem of gravimetry. Journal of science. Lyon №48, 2023, pp.6-11.
9. Mudretsova E. A., Veselova K. E. Gravity exploration, Handbook - geophysics, 2-nd edition, revised and additional, M. Nedra, 1990, p.608. (in Russian).
10. Znamensky V.V. General course of field geophysics, Textbook. manual for universities, M. Nedra, 1989, 520 pp. (in Russian)